

METHODS AND TECHNIQUES OF SPEECH ACTIVITY AT THE SENIOR LEVEL OF EDUCATION

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Torekhan Nurlan

M1703-20 group undergraduate

Supervisor: **Kiyassova K.K**

Acting Associative Professor,

Candidate of Pedagogical Science

South Kazakhstan State Pedagogical University, Shymkent

Our time is characterized by the search for new forms, methods, and techniques of learning. The modern school needs teaching methods that would help not only to teach qualitatively, but first and foremost, to develop the potential of the individual. Modern teaching aims to prepare students not only to adapt, but also to actively master situations of social change.

In accordance with the planned results of learning a foreign language, which are prescribed in the state educational standard of general education, "students will gain the initial experience of using a foreign language as a means of intercultural communication as a new tool for learning the world and the cultures of other nations, recognize the personal meaning of mastering a foreign language.

Learning a language is a long and laborious process. Much depends on the professionalism of the teacher, on the motives that made the student turn to this language, on the teacher's ability to create motivation in each lesson. Helping a student to learn a foreign language is real work, but it can be one of the most rewarding activities and a pleasure for the teacher and his students.

Most students consider speaking a priority skill when learning a language. There are not many opportunities to practice speaking, so what is done to enhance the student's speaking activities in class is very important. Communicative-oriented teaching of a foreign language allows us to use all the potential of students and the teacher for the development of communicative competence of students. Skillful use of the principle of motivation is one of the conditions for the effectiveness of communicative-oriented teaching of foreign languages.

Among the techniques that enhance learning motivation, we should mention:

- Activation and individualization of learning
- Use of non-verbal means of communication
- Project work and a number of others.

These techniques are closely related to each other, because the use of individual experience in oral speech activates the speech activity of students, and the opportunity to express their personal time gives the statements relevance. There are special techniques of activation, with the help of which you can cause the student's desire to express his opinion or thought without additional instructions from the teacher. There are quite a few of these techniques. They can be different for each student. The advantage of these techniques is that the student, actively participating in the learning process, begins to think about, remember, and use the language material studied, so the teacher learns how much material the students have really learned and how they can use it in speech.

Eliciting (eliciting)-inducing students to make a statement using the learned material and personalization are, in our opinion, the leading factors in providing motivation.

There are a sufficient number of methods of activation of educational speech among them the exercises considering the personal experience of the pupil, problem exercises, games, use of non-verbal means, etc. The division into separate techniques is conditional, applied for the convenience of their presentation, as in fact many exercises combine several aspects and methods of activation. For example, personal dialogues can be transformed into a game, the game can contain problems, etc.

All kinds of exercises have one goal: to develop the communicative competence of the student. Therefore they are introduced and practiced in two ways: through pupils' speech interaction and/or the teacher's speech. The effectiveness of any exercise can be determined by the interest with which the students comment or ask questions within the given topic. This spontaneous additional interaction is the most valuable aspect of the exercise, since real communication usually occurs at this point.

There are many purposes for oral communication, but the determining factor seems to be the relevance of communication, because a person speaks when he or she feels the need to speak. Therefore, the main purpose of communication is the exchange of information or the establishment of social contacts. Naturally, one of the methods of motivation is the method

of individualization of learning, above all, personal. In real life, any speech action of a person is determined by his own view of the order of things.

The next important aspect for the implementation of oral communication is the choice of topics. Pupils have to navigate a fairly large number of topics. They have to be "masters of conversation" both with personal information and with the ability to maintain the conversation, the ability to anticipate the further speech behavior of the partner.

All three types of reading, subject to the formation of technical skills, develop simultaneously at the initial stage. At the end of the senior stage, students should:

Understand the main content of texts that are simple in terms of language, have a clear structure and logic of presentation, corresponding to their age and interests of students (poems, lyrics, fairy tales, comics, stories, humorous stories), while guessing the meaning of unfamiliar words based on pictorial and visual clarity, linguistic conjecture and reacting to the content both verbally and non-verbally (level of general understanding);

Understand fully the content of small texts (description of an animal, a simple culinary recipe, poems, fairy tales, stories), built mainly on language material familiar to the student (level of complete detailed understanding)

Find the necessary information / information of interest in the text, read it aloud, underline, write out.

The task of the school is to teach students to read to themselves, since in life a very small circle of people (teachers, actors, announcers) need to read aloud.

In addition to the degree of completeness of understanding, an indicator of its speed is also used in the practice of work to assess the effectiveness of a particular type of reading. Accordingly, the final requirements, reflecting the minimum level of maturity, for these types of reading can be formulated as follows:

Introductory reading: the degree of completeness of understanding is at least 70% of the facts contained in the text, including all the main ones. Understanding the main information must be accurate, secondary - undistorted. The speed for the German language is 140-150 wpm. The degree of automation of technical skills in students is usually determined by this type of reading.

Learning Reading: 100% comprehension degree, with an accurate understanding of all information expected. The speed is considered as an optional indicator, however, it should not be lower than 50-60 wpm.

View reading: this type of reading requires the reader to have a fairly significant amount of language material, so the school teaches only some of its techniques, which ensure the definition of the topic of the text. The time allotted for viewing is determined at the rate of 1-1.5 pages per minute.

The memorization of language material that occurs during reading ensures the accumulation of positive language experience, the presence of which is a necessary condition for the correctness of oral speech (speaking): in texts, the studied language units are repeated many times in various contexts, due to which their semantic boundaries and norms of use are clarified in the student's mind.

A special place is occupied by reading aloud. It is widely used for teaching pronunciation and is an indispensable component of work when explaining new language material. The commonality of communicative tasks and the presence of loud external speech make reading aloud a valuable exercise in developing the ability to speak: it makes it possible to work on the expressiveness and appeal of speech, gradually increase its pace, while maintaining correctness.

Reading aloud is a necessary link in the formation of mature silent reading, but its role is limited to the sphere of only common components with silent reading. In addition to creating visual and auditory-motor images of the studied language units in the long-term memory of the student, reading aloud is used: a) to master the alphabetic and sound patterns of the language being studied, b) to develop the ability to combine sentence elements perceived linearly into syntagmas, pronounce the components of syntagmas smoothly and correctly arrange them rhythmically and intonation, c) to speed up the pace of reading, d) to develop the ability to predict, e) to teach and control the accuracy of perception of printed material.

Thus, we can conclude that reading in secondary school is both a goal and a means of learning. The goal of the school is to teach students to read silently. In addition, each type of reading has its own requirements. The role of reading in mastering the language material is great - since reading is a mnemonic activity, it ensures the memorization of language units and is one of the ways to enrich the vocabulary. Reading has a positive effect on the development of speaking skills, because all the analyzers involved in speaking are involved in the reading process. Reading aloud is widely used in teaching pronunciation skills.

The functions of the teacher in the educational process have changed significantly. The teacher-mentor, teacher-dictator was replaced by a teacher-observer, teacher-intermediary, teacher-"pacifier" and "leader" increases.

In this regard, knowledge of the history of the methodology of teaching foreign languages will help the novice teacher to navigate freely in the choice of teaching methods, rationally combine them in their work, consciously and creatively apply the recommendations of this textbook. To this end, a brief overview of some of the author's methods of teaching foreign languages by foreign scientists is given below.

West method. English trainer and methodologist Michael West is the writer of about 100 works on instructing reading, speaking, and compiling academic dictionaries. West is a famous exponent of the direct method. Reading according to the West approach is not solely a goal, but also a ability of learning, specifically at the preliminary stage: it lets in you to accumulate a dictionary and accordingly create a foundation for creating reading and speak me skills. West's essential benefit is that he created a sequence of find out about guides, which are texts compiled on before chosen lexical units, taking into account the gradual introduction of new words and their repetition.

Ch. Friz, R. Lado method. American structuralist linguist Charles Fries and methodologist Robert Lado are the authors of theoretical works and English textbooks for foreigners. Although their center of attention used to be on educating overseas languages to adults, their concept had a tremendous effect on college methodology. The predominant standards of the Frieze-Lado approach are as follows: the study of a foreign language is inextricably linked with the penetration into the subculture of its people, seeing that they are inseparable. Penetration into the tradition of the people has not only educational, but in simple terms practical significance. Regardless of the closing goal, the basis of gaining knowledge of is oral speech. Preliminary oral mastery of the language provides similarly studying to examine and write, which are considered as a technique of recognition and transmission in a picture picture of the material already learned orally. Since mastering to study and write is one-of-a-kind from mastering to speak, they must now not be mixed.

After inspecting these methods, we can conclude that the method of Ch. Friz, R. Lado is restricted to only one element - oral speech; studying and writing are no longer developed in it. L. Bloomfield's method illustrates a return to the herbal method, when they taught from the voice (in this case,

from the voice of the informant) and all studying was once decreased to imitation and memorization. Palmer's approach also comes down to gaining knowledge of the spoken word directly.

The above methodologists, pedagogics and linguists are representatives of the direct method, which arose on the groundwork of the natural one. He acquired such a identify due to the fact his supporters sought to accomplice the words of a overseas language and its grammatical varieties without delay (directly) with their meaning, bypassing the native language of the students. The direct method gave high quality consequences due to the clarification of the academic material, an intensive educational process, the use of visible aids and active educating methods.

Kravchenko M.N. A grapheme method was proposed, which phonemically relates to teaching the technique of reading. First, students learn the word orally and only then, after selection and recording, the entire word is exposed. According to M.N. Kravchenko, at first, it is recommended to use a printed font when writing each grapheme.

Currently, teaching a foreign language in schools in Kazakhstan starts from the 1st or 2nd grade, and, accordingly, the beginning of reading is provided from the second quarter after the students have mastered the oral introductory course. However, children at this stage have not yet completed the process of developing skills and abilities to read in their native language, and, as is known, in Russia, due to the peculiarities of spelling, a sound analytic-synthetic method of teaching reading has been adopted. As a result, as practice shows, the parallel use of completely different ways of forming the reading mechanism complicates the process of learning to read both in a foreign language and in the native language.

In foreign methodological literature, it is customary to distinguish the following methods: the Alphabetic Method, the Phonic method, the Look & Say Method, the Sentence Method, the Whole Language Method.

Reading as a type of speech activity is focused on solving communicative problem, that is, on understanding what is read. It should not become a means of controlling the acquisition of vocabulary and grammar, the printed text should not be taken as a sample of the oral statement for its subsequent reproduction. In the process of reading involuntary memorization of words, phrases, phrases, language realities, which later may be used in oral speech. The accumulation of linguistic material through reading is a consequence of this process, not a special task. If a student knows that the teacher will test his or her knowledge of

vocabulary or grammar when reading, the linguistic material will inevitably be the focus of his or her attention. Instead of trying to absorb the material in blocks, students will break it down into words, dwell on each word, mentally check their knowledge of the words, and translate them into their native language even when it is not necessary to understand what they are reading. Fixing students' attention on the linguistic form of the text has a negative impact on the development of reading skills, as they reread, stop their eyes at each word, slow down the pace, and reduce the scope of the text. This reinforces those skills that should be eliminated in reading instruction.

In modern methodology, more and more attention is paid to the idea of considering communication in the broad context of human activity, such as cognition, mastery of spiritual values, learning, play. The inclusion of speech activity as a means of performing the most diverse work that interests the student makes it possible to more fully take into account his interests and inclinations in the educational process, develop the desire for self-education, and connect learning with life.

In any communication situation, there is a speaker or a writer, a listener or a reader. Hence the allocation of the main types of speech activity: productive (speaking and writing associated with sending a message) and receptive (listening and reading associated with receiving it). Speaking and listening are oral types of speech activity, and writing and reading are written.

In conclusion, there is a wealth of research, opinion, and suggestions regarding reading instruction, and this summary of reading methods is by no means exhaustive. However, with a basic understanding of the theoretical framework, teachers can better utilize the most useful methodologies associated with the various approaches. Of the methods listed above, Ilya Frank's method is worth mentioning, which has received great popularity and approval from many readers.

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The sound analytic-synthetic method is the most attractive against the background of all of the above. In this case the teacher not only teaches children to pronounce sounds correctly, shows articulation, but also teaches them to analyze these words, reinforcing this process with the most common rules of reading so that the student, faced with an unfamiliar word, could guess by himself based on his knowledge how it is read.

Let's look at the process of learning to read not only from the perspective of teaching reading technique, but also from the perspective of learning to understand meaning, or "reading itself. In modern methodology there are a variety of effective methods and techniques of teaching reading: communication-oriented, problem-based, differentiated method of teaching speaking and reading, the method of the whole text, the method of oral advancement, critical thinking technologies. Let's consider some of them.

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It should be noted that in real communication, none of these types of speech activity exists in isolation. Real communication is the interaction of partners. The speaker, for example, always has a verbal intention to influence the listener, which means that a response is expected. In order to participate in communication, the student must have both productive skills (speaking, writing) and receptive skills (listening, reading). The isolation of types of speech activity in education can lead to the fact that students acquire the ability to speak on a certain topic, but they will not perceive speech by ear and, thus, will not be able to participate in communication, or vice versa, understanding the meaning of the phrases they read or heard, they will not be able to formulate your own statements. In addition, the lack of an interconnected basis for teaching productive and receptive

activities hinders the formation of each of them, does not allow achieving the proper result.

Speech activity is a complex phenomenon. It is associated with the concepts of language system, speech communication, speech interaction, human activity as a whole. The next step was the transition to communicative communication. Speech interaction is the interaction of people on each other in order to induce reciprocal verbal or non-verbal actions. If there is no interaction, there is no communication.

Interaction creates the motive and stimulus for communication. In order for communication to take place, information and personal interest of its participants in the interaction are needed. Two primary activities are distinguished: productive (speaking and writing) and receptive (listening and reading). None of these types of speech activities exist in isolation. Methodology distinguishes four communicative skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. However, it would be a mistake to think that each skill could be taught in isolation from the other communicative skills. By teaching speaking, for example, we simultaneously create a basis for teaching listening, reading, and writing.

Let us consider the principles of the conscious-practical method in the methodology of teaching foreign language. M.P. Chesnokova notes that there are two basic principles: the principle of communicativeness (constant practical use of language as a means of communication) and consciousness (conscious systematization in teaching a foreign language). There are also the following principles subordinate to the basic ones:

1. Principle of global learning objectives. Must simultaneously achieve the three main goals of language learning: practical, educational and pedagogical.

2. Principle of interconnected learning of types of speech activity. Types of speech activity do not occur in isolation in real communication.

3. The principle of comprehensive and situational-thematic organization of language material. Natural speech is carried out in a specific setting - a communication situation. Typical communicative situations, which imitate real communication, are necessary at the lessons.

4. The principle of functionality in the selection of language material. Language material is offered not by aspects of language in their sequence (phonetics, lexis, morphology, syntax), but by their importance in speech. There must be a pathway - from content to form of expression.

5. Principles of studying vocabulary and morphology on a syntactic basis. The ability to construct sentences, to use them as a minimal unit of communication.

These principles take into account an integrated approach to teaching a foreign language, which is a prerequisite for obtaining the desired result. The next step is to consider how to teach the language aspects: phonetics, grammar, vocabulary.

Types of phonetic courses:

1. Introductory.
2. Accompanying.
3. Corrective.

The first and second courses are typical for the initial stage of training, the third course - for the advanced stage.

A monologue is such a form of speech when it is composed by one person, himself determining the structure, composition and linguistic means. There are a number of varieties of monologue serving various spheres of communication. It is a greeting speech, praise, censure, a lecture, a story, a characteristic.

This type of activity also includes retelling a text, reading a text with answers to questions on the content. Another form of work is dialogue. In a technique, it is accepted to distinguish standard and free dialogues. Standard dialogs serve business characteristics.

Free dialogues can be of the following types: interview, interrogation, conversation.

Game in the school environment allows you to keep everyone working throughout the lesson, removes fatigue, fills the lack of communication in a foreign language. Exercises of game character enrich students with new impressions, give a touch of emotionality to their speech, activate words and have a developmental function. When forming the skills of dialogic speech in practice, as a rule, question-and-answer forms of dialogue are used.

The opposition between oral and written speech should also not be absolutized, since in modern life the line between them is more and more blurred. For example, in the speech of a television announcer according to the abstract or in the speech of a lecturer in the audience, both written and oral speech are used.

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